

ALL BY MYSELF

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Abstract – This is the story of my journey into Digital Preservation. This tale charts my early experiences, with limited knowledge and access to expertise, through to today, where I am often acting as a mentor. It's a call to action for the digital preservation profession to create and foster a community of digital preservation practitioners in organisations of every level. From community groups to local government, these are our grass root guardians of digital files and as such, really need assistance.

Submission Type – Short Paper.

Keywords – Inclusive, communities, accessibility, small, isolated.

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2018 when I accepted the role of Heritage Collections Digitisation Specialist, I had no idea that it would see me within a space of five years discover, learn and begin to guide others in the practice of digital preservation. In this paper I share my journey and express my profound plea that we do more as a profession for the people like myself who come to understand that they need to practice these strategies as part of their role whether it's on their position description or not.

II. YOU KNOW NOTHING JOHN SNOW!

Twelve months into my new role Newcastle Library was fortunate enough to win a State Library of NSW grant to help construct and fit out a digitisation lab. Six months after the establishment

of the lab I knew that I knew NOTHING of digital preservation and that I was in for a steep learning curve. I began to reach out into the ether for guidance and help, which is when I discovered the DPC, iPRES, Australasia Preserves and the realization that I did not possess the confidence to speak to any of them.

III. GATHER YOUR TRIBE

To help navigate through this new field I gathered like-minded people around and formed our own collaborations. This gave us a safe place to vent, question and bounce ideas off each other as we all learnt about digital preservation. It became obvious to me during this time that everyone was actually in the same situation as myself. None of us knew how to complete digital preservation tasks beyond making sure we had at least two copies of everything. I joined the ALIA Special Interest Group; Digitisation and Preservation¹ as Co-Convenor in attempt to reach more people and share what little I knew about DP and the lessons I had learnt in establishing the DigiLab and its digitisation processes.

IV. TRAIN, TRAIN AND TRAIN AGAIN

Seeking more knowledge I searched for training. There wasn't any! The State Library of NSW came to the rescue with their lead Digital Preservationist, Matthew Burgess, holding a 2-day online training course in digital preservation tools and how to use them². On completion of this I knew more but was terrified to implement any of it as it left me confused

and scared of the consequences should I make a mistake in the command line. I read and re-read the Digital Preservation Coalition handbook, I signed up for the University of Dundee Digital Preservation short course, as recommended by the DPC³. Serendipity was with me when I was lucky enough to be given an opportunity to work with Matthew at the State library of NSW as a Digital Archivist.

Four months later I emerged with practical skills I could confidently implement in Newcastle's DigiLab and a much better understanding of WHY we practice digital preservation. To accompany the practical knowledge I had gained, I completed the Dundee course and now felt I had the complete picture of what I was to do and why. Once I established workflows and procedures which ran smoothly, my confidence grew and I became more vocal about my experiences.

In 2024 it became obvious to me through the ALIA Group, students of library studies that I trained during their internships and general conversations with regional library staff that there is a huge need for more knowledge sharing, training, awareness and advocacy in my own community and beyond. Staff and volunteers in libraries, museums and other institutions need help, guidance and training in this field.

Towards the end of 2024 a vendor of digital preservation approached me to become a member of their pilot project to create a cost effective, environmentally sustainable option for digital preservation⁴. Their product would target organisations like my own who did not, and would never, have the budget for a digital preservation system. Together with several similar sized organisation the vendor has been exploring the explanation of their current use of LTO tapes as a long-term digital preservation solution. This has included much discussion on our organisation's needs as a digital preservation community sample. By the time I reach Wellington we should have established the reality of the project.

V. SHARING THE JOY

This year I am ready to start the on-training and knowledge sharing phase of my career. I am working towards helping people who are in the same position I was in five years ago. These community groups and small organisations have little knowledge of digital preservation practice. They lack financial support

from their institutions and have little to no buy-in or advocacy from management to achieve a level of digital preservation which would save the items that make up their collections.

I am in the process of planning workshops covering both digitisation and digital preservation with the community museums and groups in my local area, the Hunter Valley of NSW Australia. Surveys from these groups indicate a strong willingness to learn and practice the procedures involved in digital preservation. All the groups approached understand files they have created or collected need care, but they lack the skills to carry out the necessary tasks to ensure file safety in the long term.

VI. CONCLUSION

My journey has been unconventional compared to many working in digital preservation. I didn't seek a role in this profession, I fell into it. Once falling I discovered the lack of support for those of us who do, especially outside of the metropolitan areas. The purpose of my story is to bring this gap in training availability to the attention of you all. We need to support, train and advocate for the little organisations and staff that work or volunteer in them.

REFERENCES

- [1] Australian Library and Information Association - Digitisation and Preservation <https://digitalpreservation.alia.org.au/>
- [2] Novice to Know-How Course: Introduction to Digital Preservation workshop run by Matthew Burgess, Online in 2021.
- [3] Management and Preservation of Digital Records; University of Dundee
- [4] Preferred Media <https://preferredmedia.com.au/>

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Kerrie holds a Diploma in Library and Information Studies, an Adv Dip in Local, Family and Applied History and a Grad Cert in Cultural Management. Kerrie is an experienced digitiser and practitioner of digital preservation and enjoys sharing her knowledge in this field and the other skills she has obtained over her career.

